

Deconstructing Stereotypes of Manipulation: A Critical Analysis of Muslims' Representation in "The Kerala Story"

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Abstract

Ideologies and discourses take a due share in framing the structure and functions of the societies. Various tools of mass communication like movies are employed to cast and shed different discourses to popularize them among the masses. This study takes 'The Kerala Story' (2023) and examines the representation of Muslims in the Bollywood film industry. This movie is selected as a case study through purposive sampling because of its ideological depiction of Muslims in various scenes and dialogues. Fairclough's (2003) critical discourse analysis framework has been used to analyse the dialogues of this movie. Data was collected from online platform the Movie Box. The purpose of this study is to deconstruct the discourses presenting Muslims in the film and explore how different stereotypes and harmful misconceptions are made through this movie. The findings indicates the complex representation of Muslims in the film, reflecting negative stereotypes specially in the portrayal of manipulative figures of Muslims who forced non-Muslim Indian women to convert to Islam. The inciting dialogues of Muslim characters' are deliberately designed to damage their identity and present them as extremists and terrorists. So, this research contributes to the understanding of societal attitudes towards minority communities specifically Muslims as in-depth analysis reveals that these are shaped through popular narratives.

Keywords: Muslims, Representation, Bollywood Film Industry, the Kerala Story, Manipulation, CDA

Introduction

Ideologies play an inevitable role in the construction of superstructures (Huntington, 1996). These ideologies follow dialectical idealism and live on explaining different conflicts (Hegel, 1807). These conflicts with proper catalysts and optimum environment lead to communal violence that

“is not an eruption of mass madness but often a well-organized and rationally planned act” (Nandy, 1998, p. 25) The conflict between Muslims and non-Muslims in Pakistan and India was sparked by the separation of the Indian subcontinent in 1947. This conflict with a very longstanding base has taken many forms, which includes wars, territorial disputes and social tensions. Different yet purposeful discourses are propagated to encompass more power (Cook, 1998). In shaping public perceptions of Muslims, media has played very important role, significantly Bollywood films, often perpetuating negative stereotypes and reinforcing misleading ideologies. This research investigates the ideological representation of Muslims in 2023 Bollywood film “The Kerala Story”. This study aims to raise awareness about broader context through a critical analysis of the films’ narrative, visual and linguistic elements in which Muslims are negatively portrayed and to deconstruct the dominant ideologies that make and represent Muslim identities. This analysis provides a critical perspective on the political perspective of film’s portrayal of Muslims by examining the representation of characters linguistically. Islamophobia is a reality and using mass media to reinforce such ideologies has been high on agenda in Bollywood. This study identifies challenging stereotypes and misconceptions portrayed through film about Muslims in “The Kerala Story”. Muslims are represented as manipulative and constant “others” therefore this research aims to promote more significant understanding of representation and stereotyping. A critical approach examines narrative and dialogues to reveal how these representations affect the Muslims’ identity and constant negative portrayals damage their image. This study promotes the importance of accurate representation through media so that it may contribute to promoting positive social change and the filmmakers, policy makers, and media professionals can play the key role in it. The study focuses on a single movie, "The Kerala Story" (2023) which may not be representative of the broader trends in the Bollywood films. A more comprehensive analysis of multiple films would be necessary to establish generalizable findings.

Research Questions

Research aims at exploring and dissecting the movie’s narrative with the following queries

1. In what ways, discourses associated with Muslim identity are framed in the Indian movie ‘The Kerala Story’?
2. How does the narrative of ‘The Kerala Story’ contribute in reinforcing the stereotypes of Muslims as manipulative?
3. What ideologies are being communicated through this stereotypical representation of Muslim?

Objectives

The objectives to undertake the following study are as mentioned.

- To identify and examine the dominant narratives and stereotypes associated with Muslims in the film and investigate how the film contributes to the construction of Muslim identity by using CDA.

- To critically analyze and deconstruct the representation of Muslims via the dominant narratives, and stereotypes in 'The Kerala Story' to unveil the underlying covert motives and ideologies.

Literature Review

In today's world, media plays a vital role in shaping our perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs. Media serves sites where “cultural meanings are produced, negotiated, and contested” (Hall, 1997, p. 16). The media's influence is omnipresent and a “major institution of ideological production” (Hall, 1982, p. 64), that privileges “certain voices over others” (Curran, 2002, ; Ganti, 2012). Media skillfully contributes in shaping public discourse and national identity with masses constantly bombarded with images, messages, and narratives, as Marshall McLuhan put it, "the medium is the message" (McLuhan, 1964). The discourse constructs the social and lingual reality (Cook, 1998; Dijk, 2008; Hall, 1997; Gee, 2014; Fairclough, 1992) and the media's power to shape our reality is undeniable, and it is essential to critically examine the messages and representations perpetuated by the media. Bollywood films, in particular, have a massive impact on Indian society and culture (Ganti, 2012). These films shape our perceptions of different communities, cultures, and identities. Islamophobia is a grave problem with Muslims perpetuated as others and forced to appear as subaltern (Said, 1978, Poynting & Perry, 2007). Bollywood is not immune to the rising affect of Islamophobia and the representation of Muslims in Bollywood films has been a subject of concern and controversy. Studies have shown that Muslims are often stereotyped and misrepresented in Bollywood films (Kumar, 2017; Kazmi, 2012). These stereotypes range from portraying Muslims as terrorists, villains, or fundamentalists to depicting them as exotic, mysterious, or oppressed (Ahmed, 2013). The representation of Muslims in Bollywood films can have a significant impact on societal attitudes (Mulvey, 1975), racial stereotypes (Hall, 1997), and the portrayal of communities (Shohat & Stam, 1994). Negative representations can contribute to the marginalization and exclusion of Muslims, while positive representations can promote understanding, empathy, and inclusivity (Malik, 2019). It is essential to critically examine the representation of Muslims in Bollywood films and understand the implications of these representations on Muslim communities and society at large. Critical Discourse Analysis (Fairclough, 2003) provides valuable framework for examining the representation of Muslims in Bollywood films. CDA helps analyze the linguistic features of texts, (Fairclough, 2003). Ali, Hassan, and Majid (2024) applied Fairclough’s three-dimensional CDA model to analyze the linguistic, contextual, and societal layers constructing and maintaining power structures in literary discourse of ‘Animal Farm’. The portrayal of Muslims in Bollywood films has been a subject of controversy and debate. A recent example of this is the movie "The Kerala Story" (2023), which has been criticized for its misrepresentation of Muslims and the issue of forced conversion. The film's narrative is based on exaggerated and false claims, including the alleged forced conversion of 32,000 non-Muslim women to Islam and being sent to ISIS who are now buried in the desert of

Syria and Yemen. This narrative relies on the several propaganda techniques like Big Lie (Goebbels, 1941), repetition (Lippmann, 1922; Chomsky, 1997), and half-truths to produce power structures. (Herman & Chomsky, 1988). The Big Lie technique, as described by Hitler (1925) in his book "Mein Kampf", involves speaking a falsehood so colossal that people will believe it to be true. This technique is evident in the film's claim that 32,000 non-Muslim women were forcibly converted to Islam. Another technique used in the film is repetition, which was advocated by Joseph Goebbels, Hitler's propaganda minister. Goebbels argued that "If you repeat a lie often enough, people will believe it" (Doob, 1950). The film also employs the half-truth technique, which involves adding an element of truth to a false narrative to make it more believable. This technique is designed to exploit people's tendency to believe that a statement must be true if it contains some truth (Jowett & O'Donnell, 2015). This misrepresentation is particularly concerning given the potential impact of such narratives on societal attitudes and stereotypes. Research has shown that negative representations of Muslims in media can contribute to increased Islamophobia and discrimination (Saeed, 2017). Despite the existing research on the representation of Muslims in Bollywood films, there are significant gaps in the literature. Few studies have examined the representation of Muslims in contemporary Bollywood films, and there is a need for more nuanced and contextualized analyses of representation (Shaikh, 2020). It is essential to critically examine the messages and representations perpetuated by the media. This study aims to contribute to the existing literature by examining the representation of Muslims in the Bollywood film "The Kerala Story" (2023) through a multimodal analysis approach.

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research design to investigate the meanings and individual experiences for detailed comprehension (Creswell, 2013). Research employs Fairclough's critical discourse analysis (2003) to analyse the representation of Muslims in the Bollywood film "The Kerala Story" (2023). This model focuses on the dialectical relationship of language and society under three-dimensional framework that is textual analysis, discursive practice and social practice with process through which meaning is produced and understood via language, images, and narratives. To make sure that analysis is focused and detailed, purposive sampling was done to selectively identify and extract specific scenes and dialogues from "The Kerala Story" that has significant connection to research questions and research topic (Patton, 2002). "The Kerala Story" (2023) was selected based on the contemporary relevance, depiction of Muslims, commercial success and popularity and its widespread recognition and discussion. The data was collected from the online platform the Movie Box. The rationale lying underneath selecting "The Kerala Story" (2023) for analysis is its controversial portrayal of Muslim, commercial impact, relevance to current societal attitudes and viewership.

Data Analysis

Fairclough's (2003) Critical Discourse Analysis theory is a critical approach to deconstruct the discourses. This approach allows extensive evaluation of the film's linguistic and narrative elements, revealing how Muslim characters are portrayed in the selected movie and how these representations sustains negative stereotypes and reinforce harmful misconceptions. Fairclough's CDA theory (2003) examines the complex relationship between language, power, and ideology. This framework claims that language is not a neutral entity, but rather a reflection of the social and cultural contexts in which it is used. The linguistic features of texts, including vocabulary, grammar and syntax, are diligently analyzed to uncover the underlying power dynamics and ideological assumptions that shape their meaning through CDA. As shown in the framework derived from Fairclough's 3D Model (Ali, Hassan, & Majid, 2024), discourse analysis is divided into descriptive, interpretive, and explanatory levels that connect text, context, and social function.

Descriptive Analysis	Interpretive Analysis	Explanatory Analysis
Linguistic features are seen such as choice in Grammar, Vocabulary, Sentence Structure, Tone, and Style	Context of the text covering social, economic, cultural, political and historical aspects	The link between Descriptive and Interpretive Analysis Relationship of society with the discourse
Cohesion	Process of Production and Consumption of text	Underlying Narratives The function of Social Discourse
Literary devices	Critical Summarization of Discourse	The function of Social Discourse

Figure: Framework devised from Fairclough 3D Model

This study takes insights from Fairclough's CDA theory to investigate the language and narrative structures in "The Kerala Story" that conveys stereotypes and misconceptions about Muslims. It provides a foundational framework for understanding how meaning is constructed and arranged through representation. He argues that representation is an active process of meaning-making, facilitated through language and images, and inherently shaped by social and cultural contexts. This approach underscores the importance of considering the contexts in which representations are both produced and engrossed. The in-depth analysis of selected dialogues is given below;

Scene 1

Dialogue 3

شالینی (فاطمہ با) : سر میری بیٹی مجھ سے چھین لی گئی ہے۔ اور جو لوگ اسکو لے کے گئے ہیں نا وہ بہت خطرناک لوگ ہیں

“Shalini (Fatima Ba): Sir, my daughter has been taken from me. And the people who have taken her are very dangerous people.”

Shalini, a character in the movie is seen referring to the Muslims by using the word “dangerous” خطرناک. Since words choices are never neutral and often consciously introduced to reproduce ideological positions (Fairclough, 1992). She is calling them threatening and vicious and even heartless who have taken the little innocent child away from her mother. This dialogue between encoded media messages by the protagonist of the movie is used as described by Fairclough (2003) is used in creating wrong and negative narrative of Muslims in audience.

Dialogue 7

“Shalini (Fatima Ba): And sir I was trapped, I was brainwashed... sir”

Character is again used to accuse Muslims for manipulating and brainwashing non-Muslims. The lingual choices like **“Trapped”** and **“Brainwashed”** strengthen stereotypes (Fairclough, 1992; Hall; 1997; Dijk, 1998) and associate coercive identity about Muslims, portraying them as manipulative and brain-washer conveying the message that they use coercive techniques to convert non-Muslims to Islam. But, this representation is problematic, as it relies on misinformation about Islam and Muslims. In reality, Islam emphasizes the importance of free will and personal preference in matters of faith. By deconstructing this dialogue, it becomes clear that the “The Kerala StorY” solidifies a dominant discourse of Islamophobia, supporting negative attitudes and stereotypes about Muslims.

Scene 4 : Dialogue 4

شالنی (فاطمہ با): ٹوسرو کیلپ، کافروں سے لڑنے۔ اسحاق کو مجاہدین اور میں سنت بننے جا رہی تھی۔

(To serve Caliph, to fight the infidels. Ishaq was to become a mujahideen and I had to embrace sunnah.)

The words like مجاہدین refers to Islamic fighters or Jihadist who fight against کافر (infidels) amplify the extremist ideologies that they are blindly submissive to their “Caliph” and the overall dialogue is advocating violence against non Muslims. Words are social practices (Fairclough, 1992, AND van Dijk, 1998) and this dialogue leaves an impression of Muslims as mere blind followers and non progressive.

Scene 5

Following lines from the Song are to be considered with reference to ideology and identity construction and reinforcement.

Line 1

زند ان کو اوڑان سمجھ بیٹھا

(Mistook the prison for the flight)

Line 4

محصوم کو کس نے بہکایا

(Who corrupted this innocence?)

Line 7

نہ دعا ملی نہ خدا

(Neither the blessing nor the God was found)

Line 8

ہوا قید پاگل پرندہ

(The crazy bird was imprisoned.)

Songs function as discursive texts reflecting and producing social ideologies and identities through lyrics, genre, and cultural context (Fairclough, 1992 and Frith, 1996). The song's lyric convey a narrative of confinement (زندان) and manipulation (بہکایا) depicts prison, while معصوم describes non-Muslims as innocent or naive. The word بہکایا suggests that Muslims are the one who deceive or mislead them. They never found God after converting to Islam. The crazy bird پاگل پرندہ metaphorically describes the protagonist, (Fatima Ba) Shalini, as a trapped bird, emphasizing her confinement.

Scene 6: Dialogue 2

Shalini explained that:

میں نکلی تو تھی انڈیا سے اپنی مرضی سے اور نکلنے سے پہلے خوب تیاری بھی کی پر میں جو سوچ رہی تھی جو چاہ رہی تھی سب میری دماغ میں پروگرامنگ کی طرح سیٹ کیا گیا تھا میرا خود سے کنٹرول ہی چلا گیا تھا ایسا جیسے کوئی انوزیبل ریموٹ سے مجھے چلا رہا ہو۔ میں اکیلی نہیں ہوں اس کھیل میری جیسی ہزاروں لڑکیاں ہیں جو اپنے گھر سے بھاگ کر اس ریگستان میں دفن ہو چکی ہیں۔

(I left India under my own will, and I did a lot of preparation before leaving. But whatever I was thinking and wishing was seemed to have fed into my brain like programming. I had lost control over myself as if an invisible remote was controlling me. I'm not alone in this game, there are thousands of girls like me who have fled their homes only to be buried in this desert.)

Words perform actions and bridge meaning between subjects and actions (Fairclough, 1992; Hall, 1997; van Dijk, 1998; Bourdieu, 1991; Butler, 1997; Foucault, 1972). The protagonist claims that she has left India on her own and prepared herself for it too because her thoughts and actions were programmed. Admitting میرا خود سے کنٹرول ہی چلا گیا تھا (I lost control over myself) transcribes a situation of helplessness. Oppression and subjugation via aforementioned words portray the community individuals as less civilized, barbaric, and inhuman, legitimizing hatred and curse against them through discursive othering and ideological framing (Said, 1978; Fairclough, 1992; van Dijk, 1993; Hall, 1997; Foucault, 1972). She describes her situation as a کھیل play a game of

میں اکیلی نہیں (I am not alone), revealing that there are numerous girls who had fallen victim to the same manipulation game and are now dead, exaggerating the situation by highlighting the large number of victims so, that people will believe it to be true (Hitler, 1925).

Scene 9 : Dialogue 2

شالینی (فاطمہ با): تم لوگ حرام نہیں سمجھتے گانا بجانا اور سننا؟

(Shalini (Fatima Ba): Don't you consider things like music and song forbidden?)

Dialogue 3

ہم لوگوں نے اسلام کا دین اور رباب تو اپنایا ہے پر رباب بجانا نہیں چھوڑا

(While we have accepted the path and grab of Islam still didn't quit playing rabab.)

Shalini inquires if Muslim ladies consider music حرام means forbidden or sinful. The ladies' response is misleading, as they were followers of the Islam but still engaging with music, telling about playing the رباب (a musical instrument) as an example, that shows inaccurate information about Islam, suggesting that music is permissible but in fact, many interpretations of Islam consider it حرام. This contributes to a fake representation of Islam and reinforces a false identity as a part of propaganda (Said, 1978; Hall, 1997; Fairclough, 1992; van Dijk, 1998; Foucault, 1972).

Scene 10: Dialogue 1

اسحاق: جہاد کے لیے تو جان قربان ہے۔

(Ishaq: I would sacrifice my life for Jihad)

The following line establishes the connection of Jihad with death and killing and being killed. The movie promotes a deceptive ideology, portraying جہاد as a violent act, where Muslims are willing to sacrifice their lives to take the lives of others having a lack of empathy and insensitivity. Thus, Jihad is portrayed as a tool for using social entropy to attain political power (Said, 1978; Fairclough, 1992; Jackson, 2005). But, in reality, Jihad is selfless act driven by a desire for justice.

Dialogue 4

مسلمان ڈرائیور: انھیں پتہ ہے کہ طالب لوگ جاہل ہوتے ہیں۔

Muslim driver: They know that the Talib people are savages.

In this dialogue, a lexical attempt is made to contribute to orientation of Muslims. The speakers utters derogatory stereotypes, labeling the significant portion of Muslim community as جاہل (ignorant/savage) that Muslims are restrictive, uninformed, and stuck in the past, unable to adapt

or progress. This soft derogatory remark reflects powerful mechanism of persuasion inducing self doubts in the believers to undermine their beliefs and manipulate ideological frameworks. (Bandura, 1977; Kelly, 1955. This technique targets the specific portions of challenging groups to halt the growth and spread with emphasis on socialization of popular norms (Durkheim, 1893; Mead, 1934; Bourdieu, 1991). He even took the names of Muslim organizations like Al-Qaeda, Haqqani, Taliban, and Mujahideen, associating them with violence and danger advising them to beware of them that reinforces Islamophobia and misinformation.

Scene 14: Dialogue 7

آصفہ با! ایکسائٹمنٹ بھی ملے گا اور گھر کو مس بھی نہیں کرو گے۔ میرا گھر یہاں سے بہت پاس میں ہے۔ ہم کبھی بھی جا سکتا ہے۔

(Asifa Ba: You can enjoy the excitement and not miss your home . My home is nearby and I can visit it any time.)

This dialogue could be seen as a genuine offer of friendship by the antagonist of the film Asifa Ba who is a Muslim. But it seems to portrays that Asifa (Muslim Character) is using a manipulative tactic by using kindness and sugarcoating her words. As the only Muslim in the room, Asifa targets the non-Muslim girls, attempting to gain their trust. This is the initial stage of manipulation, where she is using her words to create a false sense of comfort and security, ultimately aiming to exploit the trust of her roommates for her own purposes. As Cialdini discusses that kindness and reciprocity is a way of persuading others (Cialdini, 2001; Gouldner, 1960; Goffman, 1959)).

Scene 15 : Dialogue 1

نیشنل نرسنگ کالج میڈم: یہ جو دیواروں میں پینٹنگز اور سلوگنز دیکھا آپ نے ہمارا کیمپس میں۔ ہمارا کالج ان آئیڈیالوجی کے اسٹھ نہیں ہے۔ ہم اسے ریپرزنٹ نہیں کرتے۔ یہ کچھ باہر کالوگ آ کے سڈوڈنٹس کے ساتھ مل کے یہ تماشنا بناتا ہے۔

(Madam of National Nursing College: All the paintings and slogans you have seen on the walls of our campus don't represent the ideology of our college. We don't represent these stands. This is just the work of some outsiders who along with some of our students want to procure chaos.)

The principal's statement reveals a troubling pattern of stereotyping and othering of Muslims. The presence of paintings and slogans like "Free Kashmir", "Islam is the only revolution" , "War", "picture of guns' and images of Muslim figures on the college walls is related to Muslims and serves to perpetuate negative stereotypes about Muslims. This whole scene can be seen joining two different elements. This scene tends to draw ambiguity between Islam and chaos by representing two conflicting ideals as same and complementing each other. Theorists like Baudrillard (1994), Girard (1977) and Foucault (1972) regards it a tool of propaganda with which significantly disputed elements are represented in association with sacred elements with a purpose

to degrade and denounce the sacred elements and symbols often blurring the boundaries of right and wrong. She distances the college from these ideologies, conveying message that they are not representative of the institution. She uses the phrase **لوگ کے باہر** to describe the external students, labeling them as "outsiders" that reinforces the notion that Muslims are others and not part of the mainstream Indian community (Said, 1978). Furthermore, the principal's use of the word **تماشا** further gives the idea that Muslims are responsible for creating chaos and disruption and it also undermines the political movements seeking independence.

Scene 17 : Dialogue 2

Investigator: Shalini doesn't exist.

Dialogue 3

Shalini: A robotic slave Fatima, and see, sir, they are successful.

By stating that Shalini doesn't exist, the investigator is unveiling that Shalini's Hindu name has been replaced by a Muslim name, Fatima Ba, after her conversion to Islam that perpetuates the stereotype that Muslims erase the identities of converts. In response Shalini even called herself a "robotic slave" of Muslims claiming that she is a puppet. Telling the investigator that "look, they are successful", she referred to the agenda of Muslims that is conversion to Islam as a form of cultural annihilation (Said, 1978). This experience can be seen through the lens of postcolonial theory, where the dominant culture (in this case, the Muslim community) exercises power over the subordinate culture (Shalini's Hindu) (Fanon, 1963.) In this movie, Indian is being pictured as naive, innocent and vulnerable to Muslims dominance, manipulation and violation.

Dialogue 5

شالینی: ایک سیدھی سادھی نرسنگ سٹوڈنٹ کو کیسے سوسائٹڈ بمبر بناتے ہیں۔

(Shalini: How do they convert a simple nursing student into a suicide bomber?)

By stating this, movie is creating a narrative that through power Muslim are forcefully converting them into "Suicide Bomber" against their will and she is **سادھی سیدھی** meaning simple, innocent, weak and vulnerable to confront them. They are using "Play a Sucker to Catch a Sucker" 21st law in "The 48 Laws of Power"(Greene, 1998). This law suggests that people are more likely to trust someone who appears vulnerable, weak, or naive. The idea is to deliberately play the role of a "sucker" to gain trust of the audience.

Scene 20: Dialogue 6

اسحاق: اور کافر دشمنوں کو ہمارا لوکیشن پتا چل جائے گا۔

Ishaq: And the infidels foes will find our location.

This clearly shows hatred towards non-Muslims, particularly Hindus. The use of the term "کافر" kafir to refer to Hindus is a derogatory term that implies they are infidels or non believers. This language reinforces a binary opposition between Muslims and non-Muslims, creating a sense of "us versus them" (Said, 1978). That shows the negative aspect that Muslims are the one who are always ready to go against Hindus.

Dialogue 7

اسحاق: اپنے اصلی مقصد کو پچھانو فاطمہ۔ جہاد کی راہ پہ سب سے پہلے اپنوں کو قربان کرنا پڑتا ہے اور ویسے بھی آئی ایس آئی ایس کے حساب سے شریعہ کے قانون کے مطابق لڑکیوں کو فون رکھنا منع ہے

(Ishaq: Recognize your true objective, Fatima. To walk the road to jihad , we must first sacrifice the ones we love the most. Anyway according to ISIS , in the Sharia law , women are not allowed to keep phones.)

Ishaq is shown as a manipulative figure, who continuously talks about their objective to Shalini to do .. جہاد and the dialogue "In Islam, women are not allowed to have mobile phones" , sustains a patriarchal ideology that restricts women's role in society. It contributes to marginalize them as quoted by(Spivak, 1998). This is a clear misrepresentation of Islamic teachings; Islam doesn't prohibit women from using mobile phones. In fact, Islamic scholars emphasize the importance of education and knowledge for both men and women (Badawi, 1995). There is difference between "cultural Islam" and "scriptural Islam" (Mernissi, 1991, p. 15). Cultural Islam refers to the cultural and societal practices that are often mistakenly attributed to Islamic teachings. Ishaq's statement perpetuates both patriarchal and Islamophobic stereotypes, contributing to the marginalization of Muslim women.

Scene 25: Dialogue 6

اسحاق: اسلام میں ہسبنڈ کو خوش نہ رکھنا گناہ ہے۔

Ishaq: Not keeping your husband happy is a sin in Islam.

The disturbing scene of marital rape and Ishaq's justification of it saying "if you don't make your husband happy, it's a sin," is a gross misinterpretation of Islamic teachings. In Islam, marriage is considered a sacred bond based on mutual love, respect, and consent (Quran, 30:21). The Quran

emphasizes the importance of treating spouses with kindness and compassion (Quran, 4:19). His behavior is a form of domestic violence, which is condemned in Islam. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) emphasized the importance of treating women with kindness and respect, saying, "The best of you are those who are best to their women" (Tirmidhi). This dialogue highlights the objectification of women and the normalization of violence against them (Bartky, 1990). He is adopting extremist ideology of patriarchy and misogyny to justify violence and oppression (Abu-Lughod, 2013)

Scene 31: Dialogue 5

آصفہ! تم لوگ پرے نہیں کرتا کھانے سے پہلے؟

Asifa Ba: Don't you guys pray before eating food ?

Asifa's statement can be seen as a form of proselytization, where she is trying to influence the non-Muslim's behavior and beliefs (Hackett, 2016). By highlighting her own religious practices, her question can be seen as a form of subtle manipulation, where she is trying to guilt trip the non-Muslim into adopting her religious practices (Cialdini, 2009)

Dialogue 9

Asifa Ba: Eating without prayer is a sin.

Asifa is judging those who don't pray before meals. This kind of moral policing can be perceived as rigid and imposing (Goffman, 1959). She as a Muslim doing judgment to persuade non-Muslims is likely to be shown as a tactic of manipulation that further reinforces negative stereotype.

Scenes 33: Dialogue 4

عاصفہ! تو اگر ہم اللہ کو تھینکس نہیں بولتے تو انکا غضب ہمیں جیل فار تک لے جاتا ہے۔

Asifa Ba: So if we don't thank Allah his wrath can take us to hell fire.

Asifa introduced the concept of hell fire so that her Non- Muslims friends take interest in her religion. In this, she is depicted using a subtle way of encouraging them to adopt her faith.

Dialogue 20

Asifa Ba: You are the non believer, you'll surely go to the dozakh (hell)

By saying that her Non-Muslims friend will go to دوزخ , Asifa is continuously trying to make the non-Muslims feel that they are on the wrong path, so they have to change their religion. Preaching of Islam is allowed in Islam but the way this movie is portraying Muslims way of preaching by manipulation and using a lot of wrong ways is creating a strong awful representation of Muslims in Indian Cinema.

Scene 51

Dialogue 7

شالنی (فاطمہ با): انہوں نے اس لیڈی کا ہینڈ کیوں کاٹ دیا؟

Shalini(Fatima Ba): why did they cut that ladies hand off?

Dialogue 8

شازیہ: کیوں کے اس نے لپسٹک لگائی تھی۔

Shazia: Because she was wearing lipstick.

This conversation uncovers the brutal violence against individuals who don't conform to rigid rules. The fact that a woman hand is being cut for wearing lipstick, and her husband is also punished for allowing it, suggests a toxic ideology, making it explicit that Muslims are inhumane, violent, oppressive and heartless that reinforces damaging misconceptions about Muslims.

Scenes 52: Dialogue 1

Shalini(Fatima Ba) : It started to haunt me.

This statement is like pouring a fuel on fire that solidifies negative attitude toward Muslims. Her experiences with Muslims are portrayed as "Haunting" setting the idea that she has received a disturbing impact on her Psyche. Just one word "Haunt" is creating anti-Muslim sentiments. This phenomena is reminiscent of the "moral panic" theory , where exaggerated fear about a particular group lead to widespread anxiety and hostility (Cohen, 1972).

Scene 58: Dialogue 3

عاصفہ بٹ: پر تم خود سوچو اتنی ساری لڑکیاں تھی مارکیٹ میں خالی تم تینوں تھی جنہوں نے حجاب نہیں پہنا تھا۔ حجاب پہنی ایک بھی لڑکی کے ساتھ نہ ہی کبھی ریپ ہوتا ہے، نہ ہی کبھی کوئی انھیں چھیڑتا ہے بیکاز اللہ آلویز پروٹیکٹ اس۔

Fatima Ba: But you think about it yourself that there were so many other girls in the market, you were the only three not wearing a hijab, right? Girls who wear hijabs are never raped nor are they ever molested because Allah always protects us.

Through this dialogue Fatima Ba is manipulating non-Muslim girls by brainwashing that when they don't wear حجاب , they will be molested. Only Muslim women are safe in this world because Allah always protects them. But after converting to Islam and wearing Hijab they are still shown to be raped by the Muslims further solidifies harsh misconception about the Muslims and their religion.

Dialogue 4

Shalini: Are you trying to say only Allah protects while others gods don't protect?

By stating this dialogue of Shalini, movie makers are showing that this character is subjected to the manipulation of the Muslims. After her traumatic experience and continuously listening about the Islam practices and negative views on Hinduism and Christianity by a Muslim character Asifa Ba, Shalini became curious and started asking further question showing interest in the Islam. This is clearly revealed that Muslims are successful in their manipulation.

Scene 73: Dialogue 1

رمیز: تم جانتی ہو مجھے تمہاری اور گیتو کی کیا بات پسند ہے کہ ہندو ہو کے بھی نہ تم لوگوں نے حجاب پہنا ہے

Rameez: Do you know what I really like about you and Geetu, it is that you have worn robes despite being Hindus

After trapping her, now a Muslim man Rameez is depicted as being impressed by the Hindu girls wearing hijab and calling the name of Geetanjali as Geetu thereby giving her a nickname to show affection so that he can completely change their ideologies.

Dialogue 2

Shalini: It makes me feel very safe.

This sentences marks the end of manipulation where it clearly showcases that Shalini is totally brainwashed and manipulated by the man who have trapped her by his fake love and affection. She has even started speaking his words. She was a Hindu who considered wearing hijab and burqa a confinement and limitation for the women but then shown feeling safe in it.

Dialogue 3

رمیز: کیوں کے اس برقعے میں اسے ایک خوبصورت بوڈی نہیں ایک خوبصورت روح دکھے گی

Rameez: He would not notice a body inside the burqa but a beautiful soul.

Rameez is using vague language to manipulate the girls. Apparently he is conveying his simple messages but by doing this he is trying to make them think that they will be prettier not just their bodies even their soul will be beautiful if they start wearing robe برفعه.

Scene 87: Dialogue 8

اسحاق: میرے بنا اس شہر سے تو کیا محلے سے بھی باہر نہیں جاسکتی

Ishaq: Without me, forget the city you can't even leave the the neighborhood.

Dialogue 10

اسحاق: اکیلی عورت کو نہ دیکھتے ہی بیچ دیں گے یا گولی ماریں گے

Ishaq: One look at a solitary woman and these people will sell or shoot you of .

In Dialogue 8 and 10 of the Scene 87 of the movie, Ishaq's conversation with his wife Fatima Ba is depicting that Muslims are so restrictive and oppressive. They don't even allow their women to go alone anywhere without their husband and if they do so, they will be killed at the spot if spotted.

Scene 97: Dialogue 1

مولوی صاحب: اسلام دوسرے مذہب کی طرح الجھا ہوا نہیں ہے

Moulvi Sahb: Islam is not complex like other religions.

A Muslim Scholar in the movie saying that Islam is not a complex religion like others is depicting that Muslims are the one who criticize other religions, religious beliefs and call them superior. But this is definitely a wrong narrative constructed in the movie "The Kerala Story".

Scene 109: Dialogue 3

انیشا (گیتانجلی): میرے کو فرق نہیں پڑتا میرے پیڑنٹس ہیں وہ اللہ کو نہیں مانتے جو اللہ کو نہیں مانتا وہ کافر ہیں۔

Anisha (Geetanjali) : My parents make no difference to me. They don't believe in Allah. Whoever doesn't believe Allah is an infidel.

Anisha is saying these words because she is in control of Asifa Ba in the movie, who is Muslim and is manipulating Anisha and converting her to Islam. She put such things in Anisha's mind to create a huge void between Anisha and her parents. Asifa Ba convinces Anisha that she is a Muslim and thus she is on right path with her parents are wrong and bad people. So she has to do bad to her parents to prove that she is Muslim and her parents are kafir.

Scene 129: Dialogue 5

مولوی صاحب: اس ملک میں رہتے ہوئے گناہ معاف نہیں ہوں گے۔

Moulvi Sahb: Your sins will not be forgiven in this country.

This dialogue perpetuates a damaging stereotype that Muslims harbor hatred towards India that this country is the worst and living there will not be forgiven here. The statement also contradicts the fundamental Islamic belief that God is omnipresent and merciful, willing to forgive the ones who seeks His repentance anytime and anywhere. Furthermore, the film uses the Muslim countries like Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Syria as settings for illicit activities. It goes on using names of a lot of Muslim countries like Iraq, Turkey and name of the cities like Quetta, Balochistan, and Kabul to reinforce the negative associations, which gives the impression that these places are naturally linked to misdeeds. This portrayal ends up layering a biased, one-sided image of Muslims that, definitely calls for a closer look.

Dialogue 7

مولوی صاحب: اپنے شوہر کے ساتھ سیریا چلی جاؤ پھر اللہ ایک تو کیا سارے گناہ معاف کر دے گا۔

Moulvi Sahb: Go to Syria with your husband, talk about one sin, Allah will forgive all sins.

In movie, Molvi Sahb is performing a dialogue to Shalini that she has committed lots of sins and in order to be a pure and good Muslim, she should marry and go to Syria with her husband. Only this can save her from hell and by going to Syria, Allah will forgive her all sins. Actually this a trap laid by Molvi Sahb to send shalini to Syria for some other vicious purposes in the name of Allah.

Scene. 153: Dialogue 3

(Through brainwashing , indoctrination and inducing hallucination they wanted us to leave india anyhow...you don't know how dangerous that medicine is? Sir, these medicine make any person ready to take up dangerous tasks.)

This particular dialogue of shalini in the movie shows such image, that muslims are very dangerous people. Through manipulation, brainwashing and hallucination they trap Indian girls and convert them into Islam (Muslims) and then by specific planing send these girls to Syria and want them to leave India as soon as possible. In the process of trapping, Muslims also use some kind of drugs which are very harmful. These drugs make them addicted and dangerous and also compelled them to do anything; they can even kill people after using these drugs.

Scene 173: Dialogue 1

شالینی (فاطمہ با): نیما اور رپیڈ اینڈ گیتانجلی کمیٹیڈ سوسائٹیڈ۔ نیما نے اللہ کو کبھی نہیں مانا تھا اور گیتانجلی اسلام چھوڑ کر ہندو بن گئی شاید ان دونوں کو اپنے پاپوں کی سزا مل رہی ہے

Shalini(Fatima Ba) : Nimah was raped. And Geetanjali committed suicide. Nimah refused to accept Allah and Geetanjali left Islam to become a Hindu again, maybe they both paid for their sins.

When Fatima Ba (ex-Hindu Shalini) revealed the situation of her friend Nima being raped who was Christian and the other friend Geetanjali who committed suicide to her Muslim husband Ishaq while crying, she admitted that Nima who was a Christian never accepted Islam and the other friend Geetanjali who became the Hindu again, was the reason behind their tragedy. By using this dialogue the movie aims to show that Shalini was brainwashed that much that she was even considering the whole scenario سزا کی پاپوں کی سزا that is constructing and reinforcing negative image of the Muslims.

Scene 213: Dialogue 2

غلام: یہ لوگ ہمیں جان سے نہیں مارتے آتماؤں کو روز مارتے ہیں۔ ہم ان کے غلام ہیں اس لیے یہ ہمیں مفت میں نوچتے ہیں۔ یہاں جن کے مرد جنگ میں مر جاتے ہیں ان کو یا تو ان کا سیکس سلپو بننا پڑتا ہے یا بدنو پر ہم باندھ کر اللہ اکبر بول کر کافروں پر کود جانا پڑتا ہے۔ اسکے علاوہ یہاں پر عورت کے پاس کوئی تیسری چوائس نہیں ہے۔

Slave: These people don't kill us but they kill our souls every day. We are their slaves so they abuse us for free. Here if husbands die in battle their wives either have to become full time sex slaves or wrap bombs on body and jump into the fields yelling "God is great". Other than that a woman here has no third choice.

A slave woman, who was a non-Muslim converted to Islam, expresses her feelings to Shalini (Fatima Ba) about their condition under Muslim rule. She claims that Muslims kill their souls by using a hindi word *آتماؤں* , but not their bodies, this dialogue is showing the emotional and psychological torture done by the Muslims to the confined women. Moreover, she blames that Muslims make them sex-slaves after their husband died in the war and force them to become suicide bombers by saying *الله اكبر* that reinforces negative stereotypes and misinformation about Muslims and their treatment of women.

Findings

This study critically examined the representation of Muslims in the controversial movie "The Kerala Story". There is a gross exaggeration of facts in the selected movie. The in-depth analysis of dialogues reveals that words choices to represent Muslims and their thinking are highly ideological. It is a kind of deliberate attempt to vilify Islam and belittle the Muslims. Their every action in the movie portrays them evil and wicked. Muslims' negative role is emphasized and reemphasized through islamophobic dialogues intentionally meant to perpetuate stereotypical image of Muslims. It misrepresents the Muslims practices to create sensation and controversy. The stigmatization of Muslims through incorrect facts and misconception is an attempt to distort their identity. Movie producers 'biases and prejudice for Muslim is evident through every scene. Muslims' representation as manipulators, terrorists, extremist, brutal and greedy is normalized through the narratives. They are shown engaged in all types of negative and immoral activities. Their brutality and savageness is especially depicted through their behavior towards females. Their criminality is reflected through the coercive efforts to covert non-Muslims to Islam. In nutshell, the movie represents Muslims the most brutal and vicious beings on earth. This selective representation frames Muslims as barbaric in the cinematic narratives. This unfair and false portrayal damages Muslim identity. This all leads to intolerance and enlarge the gulf between the ruler and oppressors. The minorities through such representation feel threatened in society as such discourses fuel anger and hate among members of different communities.

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